

Photon Doppler Effect Doesn't Exist

Didier François Viel

Keywords : Doppler Effect, Quantum Mechanics, Conservation of Energy Law, Red-shifting

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20854131

email : arcopodias@gmail.com

“One point at which our magicians attempt their sleight-of-hand is when they slide quickly from the Hubble redshift-distance relation to redshift-velocity of expansion. There are now five or six whole classes of objects that violate this absolutely basic assumption” [1]

Halton Christian Arp

This version 2 doesn't conclude definitely on the non reality of the Doppler Effect for photons since there are some points to clarify. Why is that? Because there are still phenomenons, like Doppler broadening in particular, which needs more works to look at before attributing it or not to the Doppler Effect. Even if there are still some doubts, however, we show strong arguments against the reality of the Doppler Effect for photons. Also, most of the text of the version 1 is conserved, with additional elements and some corrections.

1 Abstract

This idea of the non Doppler Effect for a light photon has been promoted by Rongqing Dai's thought experiment [2]. This thought experiment is expressed by this question: can it be true that the photon energy can “*randomly increase or decrease everywhere at anytime*”?

This energy dilemma for a photon, as shown by Rongqing Dai, is created when a moving vessel A emit a photon which can be measured by a vessel B having a relative velocity with respect to the source A. The Doppler Effect says that the measured frequency in B will be different from the one emitted in A. Since the photon energy is proportional to the frequency, according to Planck's formula, then, there is no conservation of energy and energy is lost or created solely because there is a relative velocity between the source and the observer (which relative velocity can be unknown by each vessels)!

It can be worse than that, since if we put reflectors on both vessels, until the photon is emitted by the source A, then the photon will go back and forth between the two vessels, with the energy of the photon increasing at each reflection and going to infinity if the two vessels are approaching. This is quite impossible!

Then, Rongqing Dai thought experiment leads to a more general questioning about the validity of the energy conservation law, the Planck energy formula and the reality of the Doppler Effect for photons.

For the validity of the Quantum Mechanics energy model for a photon, $E = h\nu$, this formula has been proposed by Planck to solve the ultraviolet catastrophe for the black body emission/absorption and cannot be called into question.

For the validity of the conservation of energy law needless to say that it has been verified so much times that we can't even think of it.

This anomaly of the energy in the life of a photon could be explained by the sole fact that there can't be any Doppler Effect for a reflected light photon since photons can't possess an infinity of frequencies! Indeed, since matter is quantized and can absorb only frequencies which are adapted to their quantic

level of energy, then, there would be an infinity of lost photons in the universe if the Doppler Effect for photons were real!

We will refute this anomaly by trying to show that the Doppler Effect cannot really exist for a light photon. Needless to say that instantaneously we think of experiences or manufactured devices which supposedly are working with an effective Doppler Effect, which affirmation will be contested here.

2 Evidence of No Photon Doppler Effect

An experiment done by Hippolyte Fizeau in 1851 [3], with the objective to measure a supposed entrainment of the ether by moving water, is corresponding to Ronging Dai's thought experiment and is demonstrating the non existence of the Doppler Effect for photons.

This experiment was initiated when Augustin Fresnel gave a mathematical expression for the phenomenon of aberration of light in a telescope, which was observed with a telescope filled with water. Since it was explained by A. Fresnel by a partial dragging of the ether at this time and by the motion of the earth around the sun, H. Fizeau conducted an interference experiment with light passing through moving water for verification. The results were perfectly in accordance with Fresnel's mathematical model.

We should stress here, that there have been some papers which are explaining this Fizeau experiment, by a frequency shift due to the Doppler Effect viewed from the moving water atoms [4]. But, looking at the original Fizeau paper, we can notice that he used an interferometer, which have given rise to interference pattern, which would be impossible if there was a change in frequency between the two arms. Besides, if there was a Doppler Effect on a water atom it will emit a new wave at this Doppler frequency to the other atoms in the vicinity. Then, this effect would be cumulative and the frequency would be rising or diminishing a lot in function of the relative water velocity and the length of the light path!

At almost the same time, the Doppler Effect, which was discovered by Christian Doppler, was tested in 1845 for sound wave by Buys Ballot [5]. Then, with a reasoning, which can't be found in literature, the Fizeau experiment above was interpreted like a Doppler Effect, because the wave length was modified by the moving water! It is the reason why it is often called the Doppler-Fizeau Effect.

This correlation between the two effects, appeared only because in both cases, the Doppler Effect and the Fizeau Effect, the wave length is modified. But there is a big difference in the change of wave length in the two cases. In the Doppler Effect it is a kinematic effect which is changing the wave length and the frequency. In the Fizeau experiment we will see that there is no change in frequency inside the moving water relatively to the source! The change in wave length is due to a slower speed of light in the refractive material.

To compare Rongqing Dai's thought experiment with the Fizeau experiment, we have to consider the vessel A as the laboratory and the vessel B as the current of water flowing with a positive or negative value with respect to the laboratory. In the two configurations, R. Dai's thought experiment and H. Fizeau's experiment with moving water, the light is entering in a "measuring device" which is moving relatively to the source.

Then, why does the Fizeau experiment of light propagating in a moving water flow can justify the non existence of a Doppler Effect for a photon?

The propagation of light in water must comply with what is called the Refraction Phenomenon of light when propagating in matter. In the classic Refraction Phenomenon, the speed of light is slowed down by the atoms of matter encountered by light and interacting with the photon , such that:

$$c' = \frac{c}{n} \quad (1)$$

With c the speed of light, n the indices of refraction and c' the speed of light in the refractive material.

Also the wave length of the light in the refractive material, at rest with respect to the source, is augmented, but the frequency of the refracted wave stays the same, respecting the law of conservation of energy.

This phenomenon is physically explained by the interaction between the incident photon wave and the atoms of the refractive material in the photon path [6]: “*Light slows as it travels through a medium other than vacuum (such as air, glass or water). This is not because of scattering or absorption. Rather it is because, as an electromagnetic oscillation, light itself causes other electrically charged particles such as electrons, to oscillate. The oscillating electrons emit their own electromagnetic waves which interact with the original light. The resulting combined wave has a lower speed. When light returns to a vacuum and there are no electrons nearby, this slowing effect ends and its speed returns to c*”.

Now what happens to the frequency of the light wave in the Refraction Phenomenon if matter is moving relatively to the source as in H. Fizeau experiment?

H. Fizeau observed that there was interference pattern with the superposition of the two light rays, one going through water flowing in the direction of the light ray and the other through water flowing in the opposite direction. He also observed that the interference pattern changed with the water speed. He then try to compare the results to the Fresnel theory about the entrainment of light by the ether.

Surprisingly, at the time, the measured results corresponded exactly to the Fresnel mathematics formula, and which is given by:

$$c' = \frac{c}{n} \pm (1 - 1/n^2)v \quad (2)$$

With v the relative velocity of the refractive material with respect to the light source.

Nowadays, this result has been explained by Declan Traill [7], by the atom time response to the electromagnetic sollicitation of matter atoms as described above . In this model, each atom interaction in the photon wave light path generates a new wave, in which the frequency of the refracted light stays the same, even with the motion of the refractive material with respect to the source. When light encounters matter atoms of the refractive material, at the interface between “space” and the refractive material, the incident light wave is replaced by the summation of all the emitted wave by the many atoms interacting and the incident wave, but with the conservation of the frequency of the initial wave.

Due to the individual atoms time response Δt in the path of a photon electromagnetic wave, the total delay for a light beam to propagate a distance L in a refringent material has been shown to be [8] :

$$\Delta T = \frac{L}{c} + n_{at}\Delta t \quad (3)$$

With c the speed of light, $n_{at} = \rho \frac{\pi \lambda_0^2 N L}{m_{at}}$ the number of atoms in the light path, Δt the individual atom time response for the material, ρ the matter density, λ_0 the incident wave length, N the Avogadro number, L the distance of the light path, m_{at} the atomic number.

This time response Δt of the individual photon will lead to a phase shift, depending on the water velocity amplitude and sign, with respect to the incident photon wave, but with no change in frequency.

The new constructed wave will be emitted partly in the direction of propagation and partly in the reflective direction if there are reflective properties at the interface. The frequency of the wave in the opposite direction will be as directed by the interacting atoms at the interface of the refractive material like it is inside the refractive material.

In consequence the frequency of the transmitted and reflected photon waves stays the same as the original one, with a phase shift from the incident wave due to refraction/reflection.

We can conclude from this Fizeau experiment of light propagating in flowing matter and from the physical model explaining it, that it is demonstrating that the Fizeau Effect is not a Doppler Effect, for light photons propagating in a refractive material moving relatively to the source.

We will see, in a following chapter, that the only measuring means to assess for the photon frequency is a prism, working on the refraction principle. Then, astronomers which are measuring the frequency of a photon coming from far away stars are observing the frequency without modification by any relative velocity between the source and the prism, like it is done in the Fizeau experiment with moving water.

Also, the reflected light beam will stay at the incident wave frequency, because there is no reason that the physical interaction at the interface would be different from the refraction phenomenon.

3 Contradictory Arguments

Obviously, it is not what we can see in literature for various configurations or in prospectus of devices which are supposed to work with the Doppler Effect for light. We are going to see that all the devices which are proclaimed to be operating with the Doppler Effect are not.

A light photon is supposed to be an electromagnetic wave, composed of oscillating electric and magnetic fields. It is emitted by a unique electron when accelerated in some particular situations described by Quantum Mechanics. An emitted photon goes in only one direction, in a straight way, and with a maximum lateral size which is not more than the wave length, and for visible light is under $10^{-7}m$. A laser beam, even if the size of the beam is in the centimeter or more in diameter, is composed of free individual photons, each one with the wave length as the lateral size.

The reception of a photon, or more correctly its absorption, is done in a detector cell, which detector is about the photon wave length in size. For example, to detect a single photon on a detector the superconducting technology is used. In such a detector when a photon is absorbed, an electron or even a “hole” are created and then amplified by some electronics. Moreover the time for the photon wave to transit one wavelength is too fast for any detector to make a frequency measurement. This kind of detector, if used in the vessel B in the thought experiment above, will not be able to measure the frequency of the incident photon wave.

3.1 Laser Doppler Vibrometry

To go further, one can see that there are devices which are supposed to use the Doppler Effect for visible light, like the so called “Laser Doppler vibrometer”, to asses for the deformation of metallic structures: “*Laser Doppler vibrometry works on the basis of optical interference, whereby essentially two coherent light beams, with their respective light intensities I_1 and I_2 , are required to overlap. The total intensity of both beams is not just the sum of the single intensities, but is modulated according to the so-called “interference” term. This interference term relates to the path length difference between both beams. If this difference is an integer multiple of the light wavelength, the total intensity is four times a single intensity*”. This is clearly a phase shift effect and not a Doppler Effect!

As explained by another manufacturer of Laser Doppler vibrometry it says also that the measurement is based on the principle of the Doppler effect [9] “*A laser beam is focused on the surface to be measured. If the surface moves, the frequency of the reflected laser light changes. This frequency shift is analyzed using an interferometer and converted into a voltage signal or a digital data stream*”. So, it is said that the frequency is changed and at the same time that they analyze the reflected wave using an interferometer! This is also not a Doppler Effect but a phase shift.

In some Laser Doppler Vibrometer apparatus, a “Bragg-cell” is inserted in one of the arms of the apparatus. The Bragg-cell is an acoustico-optic modulator whose purpose is to increase accuracy of the measurement. This is obtained by modulating the laser beam at a lower frequency than the photon wave. Then the beam sent to the target is a composite of two waves, the initial photon wave and the superimposed low frequency which modulate the laser beam intensity.

But, in the literature it is clearly said that, apparatus using a Bragg-cell, are able to measure the velocity of a target via the “Doppler Effect” on the reflected laser beam by the target. This is challenging a lot the affirmation which says that the “photon Doppler doesn’t exist”! The effect of the Bragg-cell is to magnify the number of photons at the max amplitude of the low frequency wave with each photons possessing the phase shift due to reflection and proportional to the atoms velocity at the interface.

To summarize the Bragg-cell impact on the measurement, one of the beam, the one going to the target, is frequency shifted by passing through the Bragg-cell modulator. After being reflected by the target, this modulated beam is made to interfere with the reference beam. To simplify, if the beams coming from the two arms of the interferometer have the same amplitude, "then the intensity on the detector would be" [10]:

$$i(t) = 1 + \sin [2\pi\nu_B t + \phi(t)] \quad (4)$$

With ν_B the frequency shift introduced by the Bragg-cell, ϕ the phase difference between the two beams which is the integration of all the small phase differences introduced by the moving atoms which are proportional to the target velocity. "When the phase fluctuation is periodic, it cause modulation of the intermediate frequency" [10]:

$$\nu_{interfere} = \nu_B + d\phi(t)/dt \quad (5)$$

In consequence the target velocity can be extracted from the received signal.

The measurement of such Laser Doppler Vibrometer using Bragg-cell is done "in fine" by an interferometer. There is still no Doppler Effect but phase shifting! But, at this stage, the question we must have is the following: does an experimenter can be fooled by this phase shift instead of a Doppler frequency shift?

In conclusion, for a Laser Doppler Vibrometer, it is clearly said that [9]: "the core of a laser vibrometer is the interferometer, which uses optical interference to measure the movements of the surface of the object. A measurement beam and a reference beam are superimposed. Movements of the measurement object generate characteristic light-dark patterns on the detector, which are used to determine the vibration speed and direction. These light-dark pattern occurs by phase differencies between the two waves due to motion". There is no Doppler Effect in a Laser Vibrometer!

A laser beam can also asses the speed of a vehicle by measuring the time between emission and reception with several burst, like in a laser gun for car velocity controll on the road, but not with the Doppler Effect as it is often said [11].

3.2 Laser Doppler Cooling

A Laser Doppler Cooling theory for cooling gazes by lasers radiation has been developped in 1985 by Chu et al [12]. It is based on the principle of detuning the laser frequency just below an absorbtion frequency line of an atom such that only atoms coming in the direction of the laser beam will, with the help of the doppler shift, absorb a photon and then get an impulse in the opposite direction slowing it. In theory if you have two laser beams facing each other you could completely stopped an atom.

It is easy to show that it can't work like that, since atoms in the gaz may have very different velocities and even if you put many lasers around, many atoms would not have the correct frequency shift and then will go away!

We can find a lot of article which are claiming to use the Doppler shift for cooling atoms. At first sight it seems it could works with the Doppler Effect, but important discrepancies between the theory using the Doppler Effect and the experiments have appeared, as said by Philipp L. Gould et al [13]: "We have measured the temperature of a gas of sodium atoms released from "optical molasses" to be as low as 43 20 pK. Surprisingly, this strongly violates the generally accepted theory of Doppler cooling which predicts a limit of 240 pK". It is why now physicist no more call it "laser Doppler cooling" but "sub-Doppler laser-cooling". It is a way of not losing face!

Then, it seems that the true phenomenon occuring in laser atom cooling is not yet fully understood and the comments above ensure that it is not a Doppler Effect at all.

3.3 Frequency Measuring Device

A light photon is supposed to be an electromagnetic wave, composed of oscillating electric and magnetic fields. It is emitted by a unique electron when accelerated in some particular situations described by Quantum Mechanics. An emitted photon goes in only one direction, in a straight line, and with a maximum lateral size which is not more than the wave length, and for visible light is under 10^{-6} m. A laser beam, even if the size of the beam is in the centimeter or more in diameter, is composed of free individual photons with the wave length as the lateral size.

The reception of a photon, or more correctly its absorption, is done in a detector cell, which detector is about the photon wave length in size. For example, to detect a single photon on a detector the superconducting technology is used. In such a detector when a photon is absorbed, an electron or even a "hole" are created and then amplified by some electronics. But, the time for the photon wave to transit one wavelength is too fast for any detector to make a frequency measurement. This kind of detector, if used in the vessel B in the thought experiment above, will not be able to measure the frequency of the incident photon wave.

Clearly, there are no apparatus to measure the photon frequency, except to focus the photon on a prism, with a known refractivity factor. Since the deviation of a photon in a prism is depending on its frequency, it is the means to get the frequency of a light photon. It is exactly what astrophysicists are using for the frequency measurements of the light coming from stars. But, with the Fizeau experiment with flowing water we have seen above that there is no change in frequency in the refractive material, even if it has a relative velocity with the source!

The frequency of photons coming from far away stars, measured by astrophysicists, is the real frequency of these photons at the instant of reception of the photons. So, why is there a frequency shift for light coming from far away stars?

The trouble with this, is that Christian Doppler itself claimed that the Doppler Effect applies to light. In consequence, when Hubble observed there was redshifting of the light beams coming from all the stars, he concluded that all the stars were going away from the Earth! But, one should know that the nearest Galaxy from Earth, Andromeda, is coming right through our Galaxy and there is no blue shifting!

Nowadays, redshifting from stars is no more attributed by astronomers to the Doppler Effect but to the expansion of the universe according to Einstein General Relativity, which is supposed to stretch the wave length of the photons! Again, this is impossible, because there would be an infinity of possible wave lengths from the stretching, which could not be all absorbed by matter!

It is important to note that the redshifting of light coming from stars, observed by astronomers, can be explained differently from the supposed "Doppler Effect" or to Einstein General Relativity theory, but simply by a loss of energy of the electromagnetic wave of the photon when it passes by a free electron in the galactic interspace [14].

4 Conclusion

It is a challenge to say that a light photon can't be altered by the Doppler Effect at reflection by a matter body in motion, since this interpretation is as anchored in people's mind!

If the Doppler Effect were true for photons, then, the Rongqing Dai's thought experiment would prove that the law of conservation of energy or the Quantum model of the photon energy is untrue.

This anomaly of the energy in the life of a photon could be explained by the sole fact that there can't be any Doppler Effect for a reflected light photon since photons can't possess an infinity of frequencies! Indeed, because matter is quantized and can absorb only frequencies which are adapted to their quantic level of energy. Then, there would be an infinity of lost photons in the universe if the Doppler Effect for photons were true! Nevertheless it's hard to believe in the non existence of the Doppler Effect!

It has been shown that the so called "Laser Doppler Vibrometer" instrument, supposed to use the

Doppler Effect for a light photon, are using an interferometer, indicating that they are measuring in reality a phase shift coming from the reflected wave photons due to motion of the target. This is due to the refraction/reflection phenomenon and is clearly demonstrated by the Fizeau experiment with moving water for refraction.

Only a prism is able to measure the frequency of a wave photon, using the refraction phenomenon, which separate different frequencies. When the prism move relatively to the source, the frequency is unchanged by the relative motion as shown in the Hippolyte Fizeau experiment. Then, astronomers are measuring the real frequency at the instant of measurement of the light coming from far away stars. And nowadays, the red-shifting is no more attributed by astronomers to the Doppler Effect but to the expansion of the universe according to Einstein General Relativity, which is supposed to stretch the wave length of the photons! This is quite impossible also, because there would be an infinity of possible wave lengths from the stretching, all of them could not be absorbed by matter!

So as to be complete about the redshifting of photons from the far away stars, it has been shown that it could be explained by an electromagnetic interaction between a photon and free electrons in the space universe, which could reassure Halton Christian Harp interrogation about the supposed "Big Bang", inferred from the photon "Doppler Effect"!

But, in this paper we don't show a complete proof that the Doppler Effect doesn't exist for photons, since there are still some phenomenons, like Doppler broadening in particular, which may not be totally explained by the Stark Effect [15] or the Zeemann Effect or particle collisions inside a gaz, or the continuous emission spectrogram of a star. We can just say that if the atom line emissions are function of the collisions between atoms in a gaz, then the laser broadening could be explained simply without the Doppler Effect on photons.

Also, about the continuous emission spectrogram, it is said by Nasa that [16]: "*A continuous spectrum contains all wavelengths of light in a certain range. Hot, dense light sources like stars, for example, emit a **nearly** continuous spectrum of light, which travels out in all directions and interacts with other materials in space*", meaning that it is not really continuous.

Even if there are still some doubts, however, we have shown strong arguments against the reality of the Doppler Effect for photons.

References

- [1] <https://todayinsci.com/QuotationsCategories/R-Cat/Red-Shift-Quotations.htm>
- [2] An Energy Dilemma Created When Quantum Physics Started. December 2025. Rongqing Dai. DOI:10.13140/RG.2.2.15188.26249/4. LicenseCC BY 4.0.
- [3] <https://www.academie-sciences.fr/pdf/dossiers/Fizeau/Fizeau-pdf/CR1851-p349.pdf>
- [4] Analysis of Fizeau's experiment for moving water by using the wave theory and the Doppler's principle. Halim Boutayeb. Ecole Polytechnique de Montréal, Québec, CANADA.
- [5] <https://pwg.gsfc.nasa.gov/stargaze/Fsun4Adop2.htm>
- [6] <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Refraction>
- [7] Classical Model for Light Transmission in Optical Media: A Descriptive Study. Declan Traill. DOI:10.9734/bpi/ntpsr/v2/6054F. April 2022.
- [8] Light Propagation. Didier Francois Viel. December 2010. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7422323.
- [9] <https://www.optomet.com/knowledge-technology/laser-vibrometry/>
- [10] Laser Doppler Vibrometry with acoustooptic frequency shift. Pawel R. Kaczmarek et al. Institute of Telecommunications and Acoustics, Wroclaw Institute of Technology. Poland.
- [11] <https://www.neuvition.com/fr/lidar-radar-gun-neuvition/>
- [12] Three-Dimensional Viscous Confinement and Cooling of Atoms by Resonance Radiation Pressure Steven. Chu, L. Hollberg, J. E. Bjorkholm, Alex Cable, and A. Ashkin. Bell Laboratories, Holmdel, New Jersey (Received 25 April 1985)
- [13] Observation of Atoms Laser Cooled below the Doppler Limit. Paul D. Lett, Richard N. Watts, Christoph I. Westbrook, and William D. Phillips Electricity Division, National Bureau of Standards. Gaithersburg, Maryland (Received 18 April 1988)
- [14] James Webb. Didier Francois Viel. October 2025. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17359659.
- [15] Stark broadening of the hydrogen H₁ line at low densities: fine structure and spontaneous emission effects C StehlC and N Feautrier. Departement d'Astrophysique Fondamentale, Observatoire de Paris, 92190 Meudon, France Received 19 July 1984, in final form 2 November 1984
- [16] <https://science.nasa.gov/asset/webb/types-of-spectra-continuous-emission-and-absorption/>